

Composites Molding—Separation and Removal of Parts from Molds

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ABSTRACT

The operation of removing parts from molds apparently has never been studied in depth, and each processor has had to develop proprietary methods based on information provided by the suppliers of release agents.

This paper presents the preliminary results of a removal study performed at Grumman Aerospace, and a method of successfully removing parts from molds using a fraction of the time normally required is described. With this technique, the excess resin flow at the edge of the part, which invariably sticks to the mold, is now diverted away from the mold and, after part removal, no resin flash is left on any part of the mold.

This paper also discusses the preliminary results of an on-going study being conducted at FREKOTE, Inc. on the relative merits of selected release agents and the extend of part surface contamination and/or transfer. The relatively simple techniques used in the laboratory to conduct these studies are described.

INTRODUCTION

With the present great expansion in the use of composites and expectations of continued growth, the high costs of these materials must be reduced. In the production of composites we have three cost risers - design, material and manufacturing. The design of composites, using computer-operated programs, has advanced so far that any future cost savings will be minimal. The material costs for fiberglass and boron composites have also stabilized and will not decrease much in the foreseeable future. Graphite (carbon) and aramids have decreased in price and further reductions are expected, but still, these materials will continue to be more costly than metals.

The only sizable cost reductions, therefore, must come from manufacturing. There is already a great increase in the use of automation in material layup, cutting and pattern transfer to tools prior to cure. Machining and assembly after cure have also been mechanized. The only major gap remaining to be solved is the part removal and mold durability problems. Molds for high speed production operations are usually highly efficient, but tooling for short run operations, which is still the case with most composites, has not progressed much

beyond the state of the art of 15-20 years ago. Studies of part release properties of molds and characteristics of various mold releases have not been performed to any great extent, and every molder must make his own test comparisons to select the optimum release for his operations.

In this paper, we will make an effort to describe the first attempts to update this phase of the industry - both for mold treatments and for part release operations.

In the section on mold treatments and coatings, we will describe the existing techniques and explain the advantages and disadvantages of these processes. In the section on mechanical part removal, we will describe new, very efficient process developments and demonstrate the cost savings that can be realized.

MOLD MATERIALS

The type of mold material and the condition of the surface have a major influence on the release characteristics of molds. The mold materials also determine the useful life of such tools, and these characteristics must be considered in mold design and construction. The actual mold design and mold handling are outside the scope of this paper and will be referred to only in connection with part removal processes. The simplest molds are fabricated from wood and plaster. They are not suitable for heat cure and are used mainly for prototypes and contact molding. For sophisticated aerospace applications, the molds are either high temperature plastic (usually epoxy), silicone rubber, metal or ceramic. Specifically, the most common materials are: high temperature epoxy, aluminum, steel, electroformed nickel, sprayed metal (usually zinc or tin) and silicone rubber. Silicone rubber normally does not present any part removal problems but is not durable, must be contained in metal shells and is used only for a limited number of parts. The high temperature epoxies are the least costly of all production tools, do not require long lead times to fabricate and can easily be repaired. The disadvantages are, normally, poor durability, tendency to check, craze or blister, low thermal conductivity, and a soft surface which can be scratched easily or abraded. Normal mold life is seldom in excess of 200 parts, but with the new Tedlar film part removal process, these molds can last for thousands of parts. Aluminum molds are more durable, can be machined to any desired configuration and have excellent heat conductivity. They are more costly than epoxy tools, can easily be scratched and develop an oxidized surface which is difficult to clean. For parts in excess of 1000, steel molds are much more durable, do not scratch or oxidize readily but are very costly, heavy to handle and more difficult to heat uniformly. Many thousands of parts can be produced, but mold contour changes and repairs are difficult. Metal sprayed molds are similar to aluminum in performance and durability, but are lower in cost. Electroformed molds, if properly made, are equivalent to steel in durability, but are easier to heat, much less costly and have an excellent hard, durable surface. The disadvantages are certain shape contour limitations and occasional porosity. These molds have a low lead time but must be rigidly braced to reduce warpage.

MOLD HANDLING OPERATIONS

Essentially, most molds are operated in a similar fashion. The mold is cleaned and a release agent applied if required. The composite material is laid up, the part is bagged, using various bleeder techniques, and then cured under vacuum or autoclave, and the cured part removed from the mold. This paper will discuss in detail mold surface preparation, mold cleaning and part removal techniques.

SEMI-PERMANENT MOLD SURFACE PROCESSES

Since molds, with the exception of silicone molds, do not possess a releasable surface, they must be treated to prevent the composite from adhering to such molds and to insure prompt part removal. Normally, some form of a temporary release agent is used and must be re-applied at more or less frequent inter-

vals. Recently, several fluorocarbon based surface treatments have become available which offer a mold surface which does not require any additional release agents. These coatings have not been sufficiently proven out as to their permanence or durability, but certain types can be suggested, particularly for metal molds. These recommendations are based on preliminary tests and show only that for certain molds these coatings may have a good potential pay-off. No long term tests have yet been performed. These coatings, tested as part of a development study, (1), include the following:

For Aluminum

TFE-LOK - a hard chrome plate with controlled infusion of PTFE by Forestek Plating Corp.

R-75-PTFE combined with filled fluorocarbon by Penn Dixon Corp.

Hard Tef-E20 - anodized aluminum surface with impregnated TFE by Tiodize Corp.

For Electroformed Nickel

Nedox-04 - Electroless nickel plate with controlled infusion of PTFE.

For High Temperature Epoxy Molds

No coatings have lasted more than 2 or 3 cycles.

The main problem with fluorocarbon surfaced molds is abrasion from layup of fiberglass prepregs. This abrasion is most severe on protruding sharp corners which, due to the application processes, have the thinnest build up of material. There is also a tendency for resin build up in concave corners. Most of the coatings were less than 0.005 inch thick, except for flame sprayed coatings.

RELEASE AGENTS

While there are on the market some 10,000 different formulations for release agents, those that are of interest for the handling of composites fall into five categories: fluorocarbons, silicone fluids, silicone resins, waxes and proprietary resins. While the selection of a release agent is generally a compromise in which the properties that best suit the particular application and the end result desired are balanced, there are differences among these classes, and it seems appropriate at this time to enumerate these.

TABLE I

Silicones

1. Usually require a "shot" before each molding.
2. Transfers to the molded part requiring part clean-up in event part is painted or bonded.
3. Not suitable for high temperature molding operations since silicones degrade at relatively low temperatures.
4. Silicones build-up in mold requiring frequent mold cleaning.
5. Few releases per application.
6. Build-up can cause loss of fine mold detail.
7. Many firms, such as aerospace and others, maintaining bonding and painting shops, do not allow silicones in plant due to air-born contamination possibilities.

Fluorocarbon Dispersions

1. Unstable in solution - have to be continually agitated.
2. Molder never sure of getting proper level of release on mold.
3. Can be a dangerous substance for worker to handle, especially in combination with tobacco smoking.
4. Low thermal stability during molding - often degrades at 93-121°C.
5. Will build-up in mold causing frequent mold clean-ups.
6. Fewer releases per application as compared to proprietary releases.
7. Fluorocarbons have a tendency to "peel".

Waxes

1. Usually require extensive time and effort to apply to mold.
2. Heavy build-up requires constant mold stripping.

3. Difficult to maintain fine mold detail.
4. Because of 1 and 2 above, mold turnaround time is long - low mold productivity.
5. Low thermal stability.
6. Waxes transfer to part requiring extensive part clean-up.

Proprietary Release, such as FREKOTE 44

1. More releases per application than any other mold release on the market. Significantly less product usage required.
2. FREKOTE does not transfer to part, eliminating all part clean-up. Low scrap rates.
3. High thermal stability, up to 500°C.
4. Extremely low mold build-up, thus requiring little mold clean-up. Less down time of mold.
5. Fine mold detail is preserved.
6. Completely stable in solution. Does not require shaking or agitation.
7. Much easier to apply to polyester molding as compared to waxes. Significant material and labor savings. Fast mold turnaround time.
8. Product provides the option of being air cured if desired.

Release Characteristics

In industry, the various release agents are used on a multitude of tool surfaces to release a variety of polymeric resins. Because of these variations, it has become extremely difficult to assess the merits of any release agent and, in particular, to compare one release agent against another. Nevertheless, in an effort to accomplish this objective, the FREKOTE laboratories has adopted a rather simple preliminary test for comparing release agents. The test consists of evaluating the number of releases to be obtained by casting an epoxy button on a watch glass which has already been coated and cured with the release agent in question. The tests were conducted in a standardized manner using identical epoxy resin and epoxy hardener. The watch glasses were coated and cured using conditions specified by the manufacturer. A given quantity and grade of resin with hardener was poured onto each coated watch glass, allowed to sit at room temperature for 45 minutes, cured in an oven at 100°C for 45 minutes, and then removed and allowed to cool down to room temperature for 15 minutes. The watch glass was then inverted, tapped and observations were made to see how well the casting falls off. For those who are interested in pursuing this, it is important to mention that watch glasses when cooling should be covered since failure to release will usually result in a shattering of the glass. The operator should wear safety glasses at all times. We believe that the laboratory tests, conducted in an objective manner, do indicate a general comparison trend among the various release agents. The number of releases, of course, should be used for comparison purposes only and in no way indicate what could be expected in actual use. This testing procedure is continually being pursued in the FREKOTE laboratories, and we present here for the first time the results that have been achieved to date. Other results will be published when available. (TABLE II)

Transfer Characteristics

It is well known that transfer of a release agent to a part can cause innumerable difficulties in subsequent operations. Because it is difficult to detect transfer, a simple test was devised to determine the transfer characteristics of various release agents. Three materials were chosen for the test: a silicone type release agent, a fluorocarbon type, and a proprietary resin such as FREKOTE 44. The test procedure consisted of applying the 3 types of release agents on a large aluminum plate and then curing them as recommended by the manufacturer. An additional area of the plate remained uncoated and was used for control specimens using Tedlar film for the release. One half of the release agent specimens were layed up with a Tedlar strip around the edge in order to eliminate edge bleed out of the resin. Six plies of Ferro E-293 prepreg were used on each specimen and cured at 0.55 MPa and 152°C for 2 hours.

After the specimens are cured and the bag removed, the metal tabs then are bent upward at 90° to the plate and the force required to lift the

TABLE II

PRODUCT	BAKE/CURING INSTRUCTIONS	COMPOSITION	# OF EPOXY RELEASES
Axel - Mold W1z (External Type 424/77)	Cured at 120°C For 30 Minutes	MAX (Liquid Emulsion) 7.3% Solids, 92.7% Solvents	4F
Air Tech Release A11 100	Requires 45 Min. Bake at 150°C	SILICONE Resin, 0.5% Solids Solvents are mixture of TF and Hydrocarbons	2F
Air Tech Release A11 50	Requires 30 Min. Bake at 120°C	SILICONE Resin, 3.2% Solids, Solvents: Toluene, Xylene and 2 Low Boiling Solvents (Almost same as RAM 225)	5F
Air Tech Release A11 30	Requires 1 Hour Bake at 260°C	FLUOROCARBON Dispersion, 3.1% Solids-- 8% TF, 29% Methylene Chloride, 2% Xylene 61% Trichloroethane	9F
Wilco RAM 225	Heat to 100°C for 30-60 Min.	SILICONE Resin or Mixture of Silicone Resin and Silicone Oil. 3.5% Solids, Solvents: Alcoholic and Aliphatic Hydrocarbons	5F
Stoner's Ink Rotational Mold Release D430	Bake 15 Min. at 300°C	SILICONE Resin, 13% Solids, Solvents: 45% Methylene Chloride, 35% Dichloro-Difluoromethane, 7% Aromatics	8F
Dow Corning DC 20	Bake 45 Min. at 100°C	SILICONE Resin, 49.5% Solids, Solvents: Hydrocarbons Including Xylene	8F
DuPont Vydax 1000	Bake 30 Min. at 120°C	FLUOROCARBON Dispersion 8.4% Solids in TF Solvents	2F
Releaseme RR 5 Hot	Bake 45 Min. at 100°C	SILICONE Oil or Resin--or mixture of both 0.6% Solids in high boiling Hydrocarbons	6F
FreKote 33 *	Bake 30 Min. at (93°C) (Can be air cured)	PROPRIETARY Resin in methylene chloride, Freon TF and aliphatic naptha	75F
FreKote 34 *	Bake 30 Min. at 100°C (Can be air cured)	PROPRIETARY Resin in methylene chloride, Freon TF and aliphatic naptha	45F
FreKote 44 * (RRM)	Bake 15 Min. at 100°C (Can be air cured)	PROPRIETARY Resin in dibutyl ether, Freon TF and aliphatic naptha	60
Dwight Products LD-212	Instructions State to Spray On "Warm" Mold to Specific Instructions Given (Film Remains Dily)	SILICONE Oil (Simple Dimethyl Type) 5.2% Solids in Trichloroethane	18F
Accumetrics Inc. 20 Release Coating	Bake at 100°C for 45 Min.	SILICONE Resin (See DC 20)	6F
ChemTrend Monocoat S	Bake at 100°C, or higher, for 15 Min.	MAX Dispersion, 16.4% Solids in petroleum distillate	3F
ChemTrend SX	Bake at 100°C, or higher, for 15 Min.	MAX Dispersion, 16.6% Solids in petroleum distillate	3F
ChemTrend SKG5	Bake at 100°C, or higher, for 15 Min.	MAX Dispersion, 10.8% Solids in petroleum distillate and trichloro- ethane	7F
ChemTrend C-7	Cure at 100°C, or higher for 15 Min.	SILICONE Oil, 1.0%, in trifluoro- methane, methylene chloride, ether, alcohol	0
ChemTrend 21	Apply light, uniform coating. No baking required	SILICONE Oil, in mixture of solvents	8F
ChemTrend 39	Apply light, uniform coating. No baking required	POLYVINYL ALCOHOL	2F
ChemTrend 45	Apply light, uniform coating. No baking required	SILICONE Oil	6F
ChemTrend 51	Apply light, uniform coating. No baking required	SILICONE Resin	4F

specimen is measured using a spring balance. After the specimens are removed from the aluminum plate, they are then cut into 1 inch strips, bonded at 0.31 MPa with AF130 adhesive (3M) with 1.27 cm lap and then tested for lap shear strength. Of the specimens tested, 1/2 were cleaned with solvent alone; the other 1/2 were cleaned with solvent, lightly sanded and then cleaned with solvent again prior to bonding.

A simple test for release agent transfer was developed by FREKOTE, Inc. The samples cast on glass dishes are dipped into a latex paint after removal. After drying, the surfaces on both release and air-exposed sides are examined for paint quality. The results of these tests will be available at the verbal presentation.

TABLE III

RELEASE AGENT COMPARISON TEST RESULTS

Material	Panel No.	Molding Cond	Adhesion to Mold -Kg	LAP SHEAR TESTS		
				Surface Preparation	Shear* Strength M Pa	Failure Mode
Control	C-1	100% Tedlar	None	Solvent clean	7.27	100% Adhesive
	C-2	100% Tedlar	None	Solvent clean, sand & clean	11.2	100% Cohesive
(Proprietary)	F-1	No Tedlar	None	Solvent clean	12.7	100% Cohesive
	F-2	No Tedlar	None	Solvent clean	12.5	100% Cohesive
	F-3	Tedlar around edge	None	Solvent clean, sand & clean	11.9	100% Cohesive
	F-4	Tedlar around edge	None	Solvent clean, sand & clean	12.1	100% Cohesive
(Silicone)	R-1	No Tedlar	0.11	Solvent clean	9.3	100% Adhesive
	R-2	No Tedlar	1.70	Solvent clean	7.9	100% Adhesive
	R-3	Tedlar around edge	None	Solvent clean, sand & clean	10.7	100% Cohesive
	R-4	Tedlar around edge	None	Solvent clean, sand & clean	11.2	100% Cohesive
(Fluorocarbon)	V-1	No Tedlar	0.91	Solvent clean	8.5	50-100% Adhesive
	V-2	No Tedlar	2.72	Solvent clean	7.2	100% Adhesive
	V-3	Tedlar around edge	1.36	Solvent clean, sand & clean	12.3	100% Cohesive
	V-4	Tedlar around edge	1.50	Solvent clean, sand & clean	9.9	100% Cohesive

*Average of 7 specimens

**Specimen prematurely moved.

LAP SHEAR AVERAGES FOR ALL SPECIMENS

Material	Lap Shear Strength M Pa
Tedlar (Control)	9.2
FREKOTE (Proprietary)	12.3
Silicon	9.8
Fluorocarbon	9.5

TABLE III shows the results of the lap shear tests comparing the 3 release agents versus the control. It is interesting to note that in the release tests, only the control and those samples treated with FREKOTE 44 were completely loose on the mold and also required no effort to remove the specimens. It is also of interest to note that the Tedlar film, which is considered to be excellent in release property and was used for the control, actually was inferior to all of the release agents used as far as transfer properties were concerned. The silicone type release left a greasy film on both the molded parts and on the mold surface. While FREKOTE 44 and the silicone were superior to fluorocarbons and released easily from the mold, from the results of both mold adhesion and lap shear tests, it is apparent that FREKOTE 44 is superior to the other release agents in good mold release properties and in the lack of any resin transfer. This is confirmed by the fact that even unsanded specimens from the mold coated with FREKOTE did not indicate any evidence of transfer. All failures on these specimens were 100% cohesive. The laminate failed before the adhesive bond.

PART REMOVAL FROM MOLDS

The recommended part removal processes are of 2 types - the recently developed film tab method and various mechanical removal techniques. The Tedlar film process is based on the study of the mechanics of the resin flow on the surface of molds during the molding operation. Initially, a release agent is painted or sprayed onto a mold and allowed to dry and stabilize. The prepreg layup is applied next and compacted. Layers of separating film and breather cloths are added. Lastly, the whole package is bagged, edges are sealed, and the mold connected to a vacuum pump and eventually placed into an autoclave for curing. During the curing process, under vacuum or autoclave pressure, the impregnating resin softens and flows around the fibers pushing out the excess resin into the bleeder plies and the excess air into the breather layer. The flow in this case is, generally, in a direction perpendicular to the surface of the mold, and does not disturb the release film. At the edges of the part, however, the resin flows parallel to the mold surface, forming a flash fillet of about 1.2 to 2.5 cm long

washing off some or much of the release layer. This resin film tends to bond to the mold and forms a mechanical lock which is difficult to break in order to remove the mold (Figure 1). Since the air has been squeezed out between the part and the mold, the ambient air pressure holds the part tightly on the mold and also inhibits release. The usual process in part removal is to loosen up the resin fillet by the use of spatulas, wedges, screw drivers or similar tools and then break the vacuum seal of the molded part by using additional shims to allow air under the part. Mallets are most often used in this phase of removal. When most of the vacuum seal has been removed, the part is pried off, again using mechanical tools. In many shops, such tools are made of Teflon or other thermoplastics, but some shops use metal screw drivers or spatulas. This usually results in damage to molds, whether plastic or metal, and the damage is constantly aggravated by repeated cycles. After the part is removed, too often with damage, a resin layer is left around the edge of the mold and must be removed prior to the next cycle. Cleaning of the molds, especially with bonded-on resin, creates quite a problem. The baked-on resin is very hard and is difficult to remove without damaging the tool surface. Since this operation is so lengthy, some of the resin is usually left on the mold which compounds the cleaning problem on the next cycle. The variety of both the shapes used and the different mold materials makes it almost impossible to arrive at an exact figure for average part removal and mold cleaning times. A figure can be obtained by dividing the total man hours used in a shift by the number of tools to arrive at an approximate value. These vary from 30 minutes to 60 minutes per part for labor. The tool repair and maintenance costs greatly increase per part cost during a long production run and decrease productivity further by tying up the molds.

New Efficient Part Removal Methods

A program to develop improved part removal methods was introduced at Grumman early in 1980 and several innovative techniques were successfully developed. A Navy-sponsored program was initiated to further validate the concepts for compatibility with various tool configurations and for their cost effectiveness when used with high rate production molding and adhesive bonding tools.

Film Procedure

Of the several techniques developed under the Grumman program, the film strip method was the most effective. This method is described as follows:

1. A strip of film, usually Tedlar or Nylon, about 0.05 to 0.08 mm thick and 5 to 8 cm wide is cut to extend around the entire outside edge of the layup, and also into convenient segments corresponding to part's edge contour.
2. After the first layer of prepreg is applied to the tool, the film strips are positioned under the edges of the layup, exposing half the film width and overlapping the ends of the film. If desired, the film strip can be inserted after all the plies have been layed up. This is shown schematically on Figure 2, A & B.
3. Any wrinkles in the prepreg are wiped out and the exposed edges of film are tacked in position with Tedlar adhesive tape.
4. The layup is completed, bagged and cured.

RESIN FLOW DIAGRAM
FIGURE 1

SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF FILM STRIP METHOD
FIGURE 2

After the cure, the bag and any bleeder plies are removed, and all that is usually required is to pull outward on the film plies to break the vacuum lock and then the part can be easily lifted off the tool. There is no resin edge flash and all of the excess resin flow remains on the film. To clean the mold, all that is needed is to wipe with a dry rag. Edge sealant remaining around the mold may need additional wiping with a solvent.

Evaluation

A study was performed on 14 typical parts and the results are shown in Table IV. First, the parts were molded using the existing procedure and were removed using metal tools. After removal, the flash was cleaned and the mold treated with the release agent. On the second run, Tedlar film was used as previously described and the parts removed by pulling up on the film. The following measurements were taken: part removal time, film installation time and tool cleanup time.

TABLE IV

COMPOSITE PART REMOVAL-SUMMARY OF PRODUCTION TEST RESULTS (ALL TIMES IN MINUTES)

PART NO.	PART REMOVAL		FILM INSTALL	MOLD CLEANUP		TOTAL LABOR		LABOR SAVINGS	
	WITHOUT FILM	WITH FILM		WITHOUT FILM	WITH FILM	WITHOUT FILM	WITH FILM	TIME	PERCENT
101	10	2	8	30	5	40	15	25	62.5
102	10	2	4	20	3	30	9	21	70.0
103	10	2	4	20	3	30	9	21	70.0
104	10	2	5	20	2	30	9	21	70.0
105	8	2	6	25	4	33	12	21	63.6
106	10	2	8	35	5	45	15	30	66.7
107	45	6	8	25	2	70	16	54	77.1
108	20	2	6	20	1	40	9	31	77.5
109	20	3	4	20	4	40	11	29	72.5
110	20	3	5	15	3	35	11	24	68.6
111	15	1	5	15	1	30	7	23	76.7
112	30	4	8	30	1	60	13	47	78.3
113	30	4	6	20	2	50	12	38	76.0
114	30	4	6	20	2	50	12	38	76.0
TOTAL						583	160	423	72.6

Results

The use of the film shows an average savings of 73% of the part removal labor time and the average time saved per part was about 30 minutes. The potential cost savings for a molding shop can be large. Table V shows some typical cost savings for operations of from 50 to 500 parts per day. The following assumptions were made:

1. Average time saved per part -- 30 minutes.
2. Average (1981) labor cost -- \$30.00 per hour including overhead.
3. 240 working days per year.
4. Mold repair and maintenance -- approximately equal to time saved using film.
5. 100% of the parts used this process.

TABLE V

# of Parts Per Day	POTENTIAL		COST SAVINGS USING FILM STRIPS		Total Cost Savings 1981
	Per Day Hours	Per Year Hours	Part Removal Cost Savings Per Year 1981	Savings on Mold Repair & Maintenance 1981	
50	25	6,000	\$ 180,000	\$ 75,000	\$ 255,000
100	50	12,000	\$ 360,000	\$150,000	\$ 510,000
200	100	24,000	\$ 720,000	\$300,000	\$1,020,000
300	150	36,000	\$1,080,000	\$450,000	\$1,530,000

Notes on Film Strip Method

Potential cost savings shown are based on 100% film strip utilization, and may not be obtained in actual operation because some parts are simple, currently problem free, and may not need the film. Also, brand new molds usually take less time for part removal. For ordinary run-of-the-mill bag molding operation, the process is extremely useful. The type of mold and the mold material used do not affect the suitability of the film strip. In the case of the so-called "Hi-Temp" epoxy tooling, there is no wear at all with the film, and the molds can be expected to last almost indefinitely, unless the material degrades from heat alone.

Wedge Process

In cases where the contour of the part is complex, or there are projections or undercuts, or the part is very large, use of the film alone may not be sufficient to remove the part and the wedge technique becomes necessary. Two or more wedges are placed at the edge of the part, below trim (Figure 3). These wedges, approximately 1.2 x 1.2 x 2.5 cm long, can be made of any heat-resistant material and are discarded after use. They are placed on the part after layup is completed, and the excess material is folded back over the wedge. Parts are bagged and cured normally, but after the bag is removed, a hydraulic tool is inserted (Figure 4) between the base of the mold and the wedge. When hydraulic pressure is applied to the tool, the part is popped off without any damage to the mold. For large parts, 2 tools and 2 wedges can be used simultaneously. An upward stroke of 1.2 cm is usually sufficient to release the part.

WEDGES ON A MOLDED PART
FIGURE 3

REMOVAL OF PART USING POWER ASSIST
FIGURE 4

Conclusions

It appears obvious that major cost savings can be realized by optimizing mold surface treatments and part removal techniques. It is possible that sufficient emphasis was not placed on part removal because initially, on new molds the removal problems are minor, and only after the molds have been extensively handled and scratched does the part removal become difficult. At this point, it is usually too late for major redesign. The film strip process, in particular, is as effective on old molds as on new tools. It is interesting to note that this technique is so simple that many shop personnel are reluctant to use it since they do not believe that a simple 5cm strip of plastic can be so effective.

The techniques described in this paper are actually just the beginning, and much more work needs to be done to optimize the mold coating and removal processes. The studies of mold releases, mold coatings and material transfer must be expanded to obtain relative ratings of various barrier materials and to determine which coating is best for each type of tool material and resin used. The effects of processing and tool shape are also important.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to numerous individuals at Grumman Aerospace for their contributions to the subject paper, particularly W. Zarkowsky, T. Lahey, H. Forsch, M. Sheeron, A. Tobin and G. Youngman.

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